

Research Article**Anti-leaky Gut Recipe 'Gut-cumin I' Could Have Helped Hastening Clinical Signs and Disease Remission Among Dogs with Inflammatory Bowel Disease****Kerem Ural^{1*}, Hasan Erdoğan¹, Songül Erdoğan¹, Serdar Paşa¹, Mehmet Gültekin¹, Cansu Balıkçı¹**

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Abstract

The present author (KU) aroused his interest about 25 years ago, during his initial days at assistant position at during early clinical experince while a grease monkey denoted that the problem was inside his dog, not the cutaneous environment. At that miracle day, author changed his mind towards dermatological diseases and searched/investigated gastroentero-dermatology. Nowadays the present author (K.U.) had develeoped anti-leaky gut formulation with his 25 years of experience, who worked hard on this era (gut-brain-skin axis) and retrospectively collected his case treatment protocoles, which evolved into this functional food formulation, namely Gut-cumin I. From this perspective a total of 21 dogs diagnosed with inflammatory bowel disease (iBd) based on relevant laboratory interpretation and clinical scoring, were subjected to rectal enema Gut-cumin I adminstration for 10 days. This formula involved nutraceuticals and 3 aminoacids participating for promoting gut health. The purpose at the present study was to determine whether this gut health promoter is tought to be of beneficiary for he management of iBd in dogs. Dogs existing iBd with a fecal score of ≥ 2 and showing canine iBd activity index, classified mild (4-5), moderate (6-8), or severe (9 or $>$) were enrolled as diagnostic major criterias. Dogs enrolled were received different dose regimes of Gut-cumin I via rectal route for 10 days. Median canine iBd activity index scores prior to (6) vs. after treatment (2) were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). This treatment modality invoving rectal route transfer of polyphenol rich Gut-cumin I, could susbtitute old fashioned immunosuppressive trials.

Keywords: arginine, curcumin, ginger, glutamine, leaky gut, threonine.

Introduction

Intestinal permeability has to be denoted as the mechanical/natural transit through the gut epithelium of moderately-sized hydrophilic fragments exhibiting down a gradient of concentration (Durantez and Gomez, 2018; France and Turner, 2017). Elevated gut permeability has been associated with disarranged gut barrier (Binienda et al., 2020). Given leaky gut syndrome, gut hyperpermeability could contribute entrance of pathogenic microbes, toxins, or inedible food material via gut epithelial junctions, then inturn reach out circulation is capable of influencing several systems (Obrenovich, 2018). On the other hand elevated gut permeability in association with altered functions and expressed concentrations of tight junction proteins give rise to leaky gut. Leaky gut, intestinal permeability and zonulin activity have all been reported elsewhere in animal models in Turkey (Alic Ural et al., 2021a; Alic Ural et al., 2021b; Alic Ural., 2022a; Alic Ural, 2022b; Alic Ural et al., 2022c; Alic Ural, 2023; Alic Ural and Ural, 2023). Moreover there has been limited literature available on web search and internet data base regarding leaky gut (Bartochowski et al., 2022; Fink, 1990; Kopper et al., 2021) and iBd. Therefore our aim to perform this study was to investigate natural treatment efficacy, by use of a novel functional food/nutraceutical, Gut-cumin I, against iBd in dogs.

Material and methods

Demographic data of enrolled dogs

This retrospective study was conducted at the University of Aydin Adnan Menderes, Faculty of Veterinary, Department of Internal Medicine, Aydin, Turkey. An acceptable favorable support on this study was given by the Local Ethics Committee of Aydin Adnan Menderes University, HADYEK, (Review No. 64583101/2022/132). All animal owners were declared to have information on the usage of functional food, namely Gut-cumin I, and about its daily dosage.

In a total of dogs met the criteria [i.e. a)

Diagnostic criteria

Dogs were enrolled based on two sets of investigation. On first occasion iBd (Cave, 2003) was preliminarily suggested i) even if existing chronic enteropathy has been continuing for

more than 3 weeks (Washabau et al., 2005) and ii) exclusion of other relevant causes for enteritis (Hall and German, 2009; Kleinschmidt et al., 2007; Schreiner et al., 2008; Washabau et al., 2005). Following triage of those suspected dogs secondary criteria was rendered possible. Briefly, laboratory interpretation involved a) complete blood counts, serum biochemistry for selected parameters, urinalysis, parasitological check (Xu et al., 2016), abdominal ultrasound specifically directed to colon wall thickness (Ural et al., 2023), and histopathological interpretation of colonoscopy. Colonoscopic examination was performed via Aouha Endoscopic Device settled at the unit of PodoVet Veterinary Clinics located at Aydin. The inclusion criteria were regarding World Small Animal Veterinary Association (Washabu et al., 2010) based on (i) chronic (for more than 21 days) persistent/recurrent clinical markers [i.e. vomiting/diarrhoea etc. and relevant ones]; ii) histopathologic evidence of mucosal inflammation [cytology was performed on iii) exclusion of other relevant causes for gastrointestinal inflammation; iv) inadequate feedback to dietary/antibacterial/antiparasitic treatment options alone.

Assesment of Gut-cumin I efficacy through clinical disease activity

Clinical disease activity, was previously well defined (Jergens et al., 2003), was throughly investigated via scoring system denoted as the canine iBd activity index, synonym CIBDAI. Briefly, six pure gastrointestinal findings were scored from 0-normal to 3-severe changed (Jergens et al 2003). Calculated CIBDAI alterations were i) attitude/activity ii) appetite, iii) vomiting, (iv) stool consistency, (v) stool frequency and vi) weight loss. Tabulated data were summed up, ended with total cumulative CIBDAI score denoting classification as mild (4-5), moderate (6-8), or severe (9 or>) iBd (Jergens et al., 2003).

Independent fecal scoring

Daily fecal scoring was deemed available for each dog enrolled and transformed into score sheet through days 0 (initial day prior to treatment) until day 10 (during Gut-cumin I rectal enema treatment) by use and management of Purina Fecal Scoring Chart, as was also adopted in a prior study (Lappin et al., 2022). Even if a fecal score of a dog was nearly 2, was defined as healthy, whereas dictated as abnormal if ≥ 2 .

Gut-cumin I as a functional food used at this study

Dogs above 10 kg received 3 ml, and dogs with ≥ 20 kg were administered 4 to 5 ml of Gut-cumin I via rectal route for 10 days. Liquid formulation, as shown in Figure 1., was diluted in 30 ml Lactated Ringer’s solution (was preferred because of its similar pH value to colon physiology).

Figure 1. Formulation of novel functional food used for treatment at this study. Functional food used as liquid formüle as shown above as whole ingredients.

Gut-cumin I	
Curcumin	1.2%
Zinc	0.31%
L-Glutamine	2.2%
L-Arginine	0.7%
Deglycrrhized	0.4%
Licorice root	
Ginger	1.2%
Threonine	0.5%

Results

Available and obtained data tabulated at Table 1 and Figure 2-5. Median, min-max and p values were set at table 1 below. There was significant alterations among before and after values during Gut-cumin I treatment via rectal route. Total cumulative CIBDAI scores were diminished [median values 6 vs 2, prior to and after treatment, respectively]. Figure 2 showed scattered plot values regarding total CIBDAI scores before and after treatment.

Table 1. Total cumulative CIBDAI score denoting classification as mild (4-5), moderate (6-8), or severe (9 or >) IBD (Jergens et al 2003).

	Median	min-max	Range
Before Treatment Score	6	2 - 10	8
After Treatment Score	2	0 - 4	4
P value	0.001		

Fecal scoring results

As aforementioned above fecal scoring results were deemed available as observer (one of the veterinary surgeons involved at the present study received or obtained photographic records and daily inspected). Cases no 4 and 7 were additonaly and selectively shown at Figure 3 and 4, showing clinical cure.

Figure 2. Presentation of individual scores prior to iBd thereafter Gut-cumin I treatment.

Fecal scoring results were also shown in Table 2 below indicating no of cases with fecal score ≥ 2 or below along with triage colors changed during trial.

Table 2. Fecal scoring results were deemed available at days 0 (prior to treatment) and thereafter day 10 (at the end point of treatment).

	No of cases with fecal score ≥ 2	No of cases with fecal score 2	Gastrointestinal triage color (per cases number)		
			immediate	minor	dead, dying or euthanize
Prior to Gut-cumin I treatment	19	2	7	11	3
On day 10 at Gut-cumin I treatment	1	20	1	20	0

Figure 3. Case no 4 with fecal structure prior to (day 0) and thereafter Gut-cumin I administration (day 10).

Figure 4. Case no 7 with fecal structure prior to (day 0) and thereafter Gut-cumin I administration (day 10). Fecal scoring was deemed available and appeared as score 1 and 2, respectively.

Discussion

Given the last era, investigations have been conducted for better understanding the participation of phytonutrients [i.e. flavonoids etc.] for modulation of inflammatory respond and protection of intestinal barrier integrity (Gil-Cardoso et al., 2016). The investigational test nutrients invoved in novel functional food Gut-cumin I has been possessed as flavonoid rich [turmeric (*Curcuma long L.*), *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, Ginger (*Zingiber officinale Roscoe*), along with zinc and relevant gut friendly aminoacids. Prior to settlement of the present study, Gut cumin I gave satisfactory results for several gastrointestinal and dermatological cases (with written owner consent), prompted and encouraged us to perform this trial. Our next study would probably be aimed to detect gut microbiota-Gut cumin I interactions in a longitudinal study.

In a prior study *Glycyrrhiza glabra* has helped in vitro protection of the intestinal epithelial barrier integrity through human intestinal Caco-2 cells. Usage of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* markedly altered the intestinal epithelial barrier function. In that study colon morphology, also involving colon weight/length ratio additionally showed advantageous efficacy of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* through barrier function. Furthermore this nutraceutical adjusted the tight junction proteins, along with markedly elevated secretory IgA levels in rats with colitis (Murugan et al., 2022). *Glycyrrhiza glabra* presented antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and antiulcer activities (Chandrasekaran et al., 2011; Mukherjee et al., 2010; Puram et al., 2013). The latter nutraceutical was capable of inhibiting proinflammatory mediator release (Thiyagarajan et al., 2011). This self-budget project was not supported by any financial headquarters, in which

we were not capable of analyzing proinflammatory cytokines during trial. However one of the mechanisms of clinical recovery observed at this study could potentially be related to inhibition of harmful cytokines. Gut-cumin I also harbor curcumin when used, which the latter ayurvedic compound is capable of also silencing inflammasomes (Hasanzadeh et al., 2020).

To the present author knowledge, an underrated amino acid as L-arginine is a principal gut metabolite, accompanying for protein synthesis, restricting intestinal adjustment and maintainance of immune functions (Bertrand et al., 2012; Morris, 2007). L-arginine deficiency in relationship with probable infection participated in immunopathological alterations, where administration of the latter amino acid accompanied reduction in inflammation and infectious outcome (Drover et al., 2011). It was previously detected that malaria-associated hypoargininemia altered gut barrier functioning along with predisposition of the host to Salmonella comorbidity. Elevated pharmacokinetics of L-arginine diminished intestinal inflammation (Chau et al., 2013). In the present study Gut-cumin I formulation involved 0.7% L-arginine, which could have helped reversing inflammation at intestinal environment. Moreover a previous trial denoted that L-arginine complementary feed conserved intestinal epithelium integrity under heat stress conditions at exercise (Costa et al., 2014).

Glutamine mainatined gut surface integrity and trophicity. Hence pigs presenting acute pancreatitis, receiving enteral nutrition [i.e. probiotics/arginine/glutamine] showed diminished intestinal permeability along with plasma endotoxin levels and bacterial translocation (Zou et al., 2010). Moreover enteral support probiotics and glutamine altered gut permeability, diminished bacterial translocation along rats with trauma related injury of the brain (Zhang et al., 2015). Among mice with colitis oral glutamine prescription set out suppressive Th1/Th17 immune respond along with diminished inflammation in comparison to regular diet fed mice (Hsiung et al., 2014). Other relevant amino acids were linked with a preservative phenotype against colitis. In colitis model regarding several animals, threonine along with other ones adminstered prior to and during disease activity, detected to reinstate synthesis of mucin and stabilization of intestinal microbiota (Faure et al., 2006, Liu et al., 2013). In the present study as a rectal enema treatment

modality Gut-cumin I was used, which included both glutamine and threonine, along with L-arginine as whole aminoacids promoting gut health. In a well described review it was stated that changing the composition of selected aminoacids, with special reference to trophic aminoacids, could be beneficiary for modulating physiological, microbiological and immunological consequences of gut ecology. Trophic acids, denoting glutamine, arginine and threonine, could all participate pivotal roles at gut mucosa level and thus be capable of improving intestinal recovery against injury. Moreover all latter aminoacids, also involved as ingredients in Gut-cumin I, soothes exagerrated immune respond, in terms of nutrients/energy balance. This could also participate in modulation of gut microbiota (Bortoluzzi et al., 2018). Furthermore glutamin may have helped alterations among fecal scores obtained at this study. As shown in table 2, prior to Gut-cumin I treatment number of cases with fecal score ≥ 2 was 19 vs. 1, thereafter day 10 on Gut-cumin I treatment. On the other hand number of cases with fecal scoring 2 was 2 vs. 20, prior to and after day 10 on Gut-cumin I treatment.

Curcumin, a very well recognized health-promoter polyphenol, possessed gastrointestinal instability and declined intestinal permeability, which all could participated in its limited usage among foods (Dulbecco and Savarino, 2013, Jo et al 2023). Emulsions prepared as oil-in-water are frequently utilized for delivering polyphenols, based on their ability of dispersion in water (Araiza-Calahorra et al., 2018). In the present study Gut-cumin I compound was also an example of oil-in-water polyphenol and aminoacid ingredient, which could have helped better utilization and recovery of iBd detected among dogs. In a prior study intestinal permeability of curcumin was improved due to mucoadhesion and epithelial tight junction opening in relationship with chitosan coating (Jo et al., 2023). At this point we, as present authors would like to discuss briefly the mechanism of action on curcumin at the intestinal level. Regarding adequate amounts of curcumin existed in colonic mucosa, intestinal ecology and anatomy are the sites for actioning of curcumin (Ghosh et al., 2018). Structural-activity interaction researches at in vitro level or experimentally induced colitis model, clearly presented the participation of the methoxy groups for anti-inflammatory activity of curcumin supporting evidenced based medicine for favourable

act of curcumin within the gut (Yang et al., 2017). Curcumin-drug pharmacokinetic relationship are indeed more or less entirely within the enterocytes, due to substantial first pass metabolism and poverty-stricken curcumin bioavailability denoting that enterocytes are odds-on targeted cell type for curcumin activity for elevated action of co-administered drugs (Adiwidjaja et al., 2017). Curcuminoids are prone to be metabolized through gut ecology for production of active colonic metabolites even if capable of exhibiting local/systemic efficacy (Burapan et al., 2017). For the vast majority of uncommunicable disorders with chronic inflammation; curcumin exhibited beneficiary advantages alone with reversing intestinal barrier dysfunction. Taking into account elevated levels in the gut and actioning on enterocytes, curcumin employs modulation of intestinal barrier function, which could easily contribute influence on chronic inflammatory diseases (Ghosh et al., 2018). Moreover curcumin enema modified and altered intestinal barrier function in a very fresh study (Alic Ural et al., 2024). All aforementioned mechanisms could be attributable to the efficacy of curcumin involved in Gut-cumin I, used at this study.

Gingereol enriched ginger diminished spinal nerve ligation induced intestinal permeability and neuroinflammation among rats (Shen et al., 2022). Another study among humans reported that ginger root powder administered to humans was well tolerated and changed gut microbiota composition without disturbing alpha/beta diversity (Crichton et al., 2023). Immunosupressed mice were administered ginger polysaccharides, in which intestinal immunity was improved via gut microbiota alterations. According to the latter study ginger polysaccharides possessed functional food features against intestinal barrier injury (Liu et al., 2022).

Conclusion

In the present study as shown in table 2, no of cases with fecal score ≥ 2 (disease activity) were 19 vs. 2, prior to Gut-cumin I rectal treatment. On the other hand no of cases with fecal score 2 (health condition) were 1 vs. 20, after Gut-cumin I treatment, respectively. This treatment modality, although in a short period, with its enriched nutraceutical ingredients, could act as a functional food. This may be briefly explained with the clinical cure, at least obtained at the present study in a

short period to subjected dogs. Further studies are warranted with long term efficacy of this functional food. This study findings might support probable protective action of Gut-cumin I on intestinal epithelial barrier functions indicating its plausible efficacy for preventing leaky gut.

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